

Title: Environmental Chemistry for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

Environmental chemistry combines the ideas of chemical research with knowledge of the environment. It looks at chemical processes that happen in the atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere, and biosphere. This review emphasizes the chemical characteristics of contaminants, the many forms of pollution, and preventive measures structured around a mind map framework. Some of the main topics are pollution of the air, water, and soil, acid rain, the greenhouse effect, the production of smog, and the loss of ozone. The idea of green chemistry is important since it is a long-term way to cut down on damage to the environment by using eco-friendly methods. Using a mind mapping method, complicated environmental events are broken down into linked visual nodes, which helps students and researchers understand and be aware of them better.

Key Words

Environmental chemistry, Air pollution, Water pollution, Green chemistry, Ozone depletion, Greenhouse effect, Mind mapping

It is a way of thinking and utilizing the existing knowledge and principles of chemistry and other science to reduce the adverse impact in environment.

Green chemistry

Gradual increase in average temperature of surface of the earth due to increase in concentration of green house gases (CO₂, CFCs, CH₄)

Global warming

It is naturally occurring phenomenon responsible for heating earth's surface and atmosphere

Green House Effect

Soil Pollution

Preventions

- . Use of manures.
- . Use of bio-fertilizers.
- . Proper Sewage system.
- . Salvage and recycling.

Amount of oxygen required by bacteria to break down the organic matter present in a certain volume of a sample of water.

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)

Water Pollution

Pathogens

Disease, Tarring agents, Include bacteria.

Layer of Atmosphere

- Troposphere : 0-10 km
- Stratosphere : 10-30 km
- Mesosphere : 30-50 km
- Thermosphere : 50-400 km
- Exosphere : 400 km

Environmental Chemistry

Atmosphere

Atmospheric pollution

Depletion of O₃ Layer

1. Biodegradable waste: Generated by cotton mills, paper mills, textiles, etc.
2. Non-biodegradable waste: Generated by power plants, steel plants, fertilizer industries, etc.

Types

THE EARTH'S ATMOSPHERE

When pH of rain water drops below 5.6

Acid Rain

- . Oxides of Sulphur
- . Oxides of Nitrogen
- . Oxides of Carbon
- . Particulate pollutants
- . Hydrocarbons

Smog → Smoke + Fog

- . Classical Smog
- . Photochemical Smog

OZONE DEPLETION

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